

PRODUCTION OF THE JOSHI EFFECT IN OXYGEN UNDER SILENT ELECTRIC DISCHARGE. PART VII. INFLUENCE OF FREQUENCY FILTERS, RESISTIVE AND CAPACITATIVE CHANGES, AND NATURE OF THE A. C. INDICATOR

BY S. R. MOHANTY

The Joshi effect Δi in oxygen enclosed in a Siemens' tube at 27 mm. Hg (20°) pressure and excited over 0.5-3 kV (r. m. s.) of 50 cycles frequency has been studied, (i) in different components of the discharge current i ; (ii) under 1 to 10 k Ω serial (ohmic) resistances R in L. T.; (iii) with various capacitances, 0.00025 to 0.031 μ F in series with, and 0.0001 to 0.01 μ F across, the detector, in L. T.; (iv) with Cambridge A. C. micro-ammeter, Westector 'cold' rectifier, vacuo-junction, diode, triode and pentode used for observing i .

i consists of high frequency i_{HF} , low frequency i_{LF} and the supply frequency component i_S . At constant applied potential V, the net effect Δi and the proportionate effect % Δi are larger for filtered i_{HF} than for filtered i_{LF} . The H. F. region of i is the chief seat of the phenomenon.

R decreases i , Δi and % Δi ; diminution, in each case, is more pronounced at small rather than at large values of R. The corresponding V across the ozoniser, determined electrostatically, is, however, not affected. Inhibition due to R is attributed, following Joshi, to preferential damping of the H. F. components of i .

A serial capacitance, in between the L. T. of discharge tube and detector, admits preferentially the H. Fs., and therefore, increases % Δi . This last is reduced by a capacitance added across the detector, since now the capacitance by-passes the H.Fs.

The 'threshold potential' V_m is not altered by a change in the mode of current detection. Δi is highest with an inductively fed pentode, and lowest with a Westector 'cold' rectifier. Potential variation of Δi and % Δi is similar in all the cases. With a thermionic tube detector, Δi is always higher with the method of inductive coupling than with that of resistive coupling. With a triode, Δi is higher with anode bend than with grid leak detection. A positive effect $+\Delta i$ is observed with valve detectors at low applied V, decreases with V, and rapidly changes sign above V_m . $+\Delta i$ is not observed under identical conditions with a vacuo-junction. The selectivity in response of the various detectors to different frequencies in the spectrum of i is considered to be responsible for the observed variations in Δi .

The present communication, which is an extension of the preliminary observations of the author (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1947, Part III, *Phys. Sec.*, Abst. No. 14) and of the author and Kamath (*ibid.*, 1947, Part III, *Phys. Sec.*, Abst. No. 15), reports results on the Joshi effect in oxygen, in the high and the low frequency components of the discharge current, under resistive and capacitive changes in the L. T. circuit, and with different modes of current detection, including the production of a positive effect, *i. e.*, a current gain under irradiation, with thermionic tube detectors.

EXPERIMENTAL

The general experimental arrangement and the circuit employed are shown in Fig. 1. The electrical discharge was produced in the annular space of a

detector through c and c_1 (Fig. 1), and Δi observed. A capacitance C of $0.0001\mu\text{F}$ was next introduced serially in between the L.T. terminal of the discharge tube and the vacuo-junction *via* 2 and 3 (c_1 having been disconnected). It admitted preferentially the H.F. and inhibited the L.F., the latter were by-passed by the iron-core inductance L of about 200 henrys (which inhibited the L.F.), connected through 4 and 5. Finally, the L.F. were filtered into the detector through L , put in series in L. T. *via* 4 and 6, besides C across the vacuo-junction through 2 and 7. The effect was also studied under capacitative and resistive changes in the L. T. circuit. Capacitance introduced in series (C_2) in between the L.T. terminal of the discharge tube and the detector was varied over $0.00025 - 0.001\mu\text{F}$, and that put across (C_1) the detector from 0.0001 to $0.01\mu\text{F}$. The ohmic resistance R connected serially in L. T. was varied over $1-10\text{ k}\Omega$; it was of Dubilier type, non-inductive and sensibly non-capacitative.

A comparative study of Δi was next made (Table V) with the following detectors used for observing i :

(a) *Cambridge A. C. micro-ammeter* (μA , Fig. 1).—This was a full-wave copper-copper oxide rectifier, and was introduced in series in L. T.

(b) *Westector 'cold' rectifier*.—This was a half-wave crystal detector. It was connected, in series with the galvanometer G , between the L.T. terminal of the ozoniser and earth.

(c) *Cambridge vacuo-junction*.—The one used had a low heater resistance (25Ω). This was connected to the galvanometer G . The arrangement was appreciably current sensitive, since the corresponding galvanometer deflections are proportional to the square of the current flowing through the ozoniser.

(d) *Double diode 6H6 (RCA)*.—This was used as a half-wave rectifier. For this purpose, the two plates, as also the two cathodes, were short-circuited. The filament of the thermionic tube was heated at 270 mA obtained from a battery of three 2 volt accumulators. In one series of observations, the current flowing through the ozoniser was passed through the primaries of a $3:4$ Bell type iron-core transformer. The secondaries of this transformer were connected to the plates and the cathodes of the valve through the galvanometer G . In another set of observations, the input to the diode was tapped from across a non-inductive and sensibly non-capacitative Dubilier type resistance of $2.5\text{ k}\Omega$ introduced serially in L.T.

(e) *Triode 30 (RCA)*.—This was used as (i) an anode bend detector, and (ii) as a grid leak detector. The thermionic tube was fed both inductively and resistively from the L.T. The filament of the valve was heated with a current of 56 mA drawn from a 2 volt storage cell. For (i), the grid was given a negative bias of 9 volts obtained from dry cells. The positive terminal of the grid bias battery and the filament of the valve were earthed. The plate was maintained at $+90\text{ volts}$ obtained from 220 volt , D.C. mains by means of a potentiometric arrangement. The galvanometer G was introduced in the plate circuit.

TABLE I
The Joshi effect in oxygen in different components of the discharge current.

$pO_2 = 27 \text{ mm}(20^\circ)$. Temp. = 33° . Frequency of A. C. supply = 50 cyc./sec. Detector = Vacuo-junction. Source of radiations = Tl res 500 volt, 200 watt (glass) bulbs 22 cm. from the ozoniser.

V (kV, r.m.s.)	i_D			i_L			Δi			$\% \Delta i$		
	L.T.	H.F.	L.F.	L.T.	H.F.	L.F.	L.T.	H.F.	L.F.	L.T.	H.F.	L.F.
0.67	12.69	9.64	2.45	7.81	5.92	1.79	4.86	3.72	0.72	36.5	36.6	28.4
0.88	15.13	11.33	3.67	10.3	7.48	3.08	4.83	3.75	0.79	31.9	33.4	20.4
1.2	19.96	10.58	4.58	10.4	7.55	3.97	3.56	3.03	0.71	25.5	26.6	16.5
1.47	14.07	10.26	5.24	10.86	7.68	4.69	3.31	2.67	0.56	22.8	25.9	10.5
1.87	14.11	10.2	6.16	11.45	7.94	5.70	2.66	2.26	0.46	16.9	22.2	7.5
2.27	14.45	9.6	6.83	12.29	6.66	6.71	2.17	1.74	0.22	15.0	17.8	3.3
2.67	15.00	9.8	6.19	12.30	6.25		1.70	1.55		11.3	15.8	

TABLE II

Influence of resistive impedance on the Joshi effect in oxygen.

$pO_2 = 27$ mm (20°). Temperature = 31°. Frequency of A.C. supply = 50 cyc./sec.
 Detector = Vacuo-junction. Source of radiations = Three 200 volt, 200 watt (glass) bulbs,
 15 cm. from the ozoniser.

R(k Ω)	0.	1.	2.5.	5.	7.5.	10.	
V							
(kV, r.m.s.)							
0.67	i_D	11.92	8.49	5.99	5.00	4.58	4.36
	i_L	6.93	4.12	3.46	3.16	2.83	2.65
	Δi	4.99	2.36	1.93	1.84	1.76	1.71
	% Δi	41.8	36.4	35.8	36.8	39.2	39.2
0.83	i_D	13.26	7.48	6.71	6.25	5.92	5.86
	i_L	9.11	5.99	5.2	4.9	4.69	4.47
	Δi	4.15	2.09	1.51	1.35	1.23	1.19
	% Δi	31.3	27.9	22.5	21.6	20.8	21.0
1.2	i_D	13.15	7.75	6.68	6.33	6.00	5.75
	i_L	9.75	6.33	5.57	5.29	5.1	4.9
	Δi	3.40	1.43	1.06	1.04	0.9	0.85
	% Δi	25.9	18.3	16	16.4	15.0	14.8
1.47	i_D	12.76	7.97	6.96	6.58	6.16	6.08
	i_L	10.05	6.78	6.08	5.75	5.57	5.39
	Δi	2.71	1.09	0.78	0.93	0.59	0.69
	% Δi	21.2	13.9	11.4	12.6	9.6	11.3
1.87	i_D	13.00	8.43	7.42	7.07	6.78	6.63
	i_L	10.77	7.55	6.86	6.56	6.33	6.16
	Δi	2.23	0.88	0.56	0.51	0.45	0.47
	% Δi	17.2	10.4	7.5	7.2	6.6	7.1
2.27	i_D	13.46	9.22	8.54	8.12	7.81	7.62
	i_L	11.66	8.60	8.06	7.63	7.42	7.29
	Δi	1.80	0.66	0.48	0.53	0.39	0.34
	% Δi	13.4	6.1	5.6	6.2	5	4.5
2.67	i_D	14.29	10.35	9.59	9.27		
	i_L	12.92	9.95	9.27	9.00		
	Δi	1.37	0.40	0.32	0.27		
	% Δi	9.6	3.9	3.3	2.9		

TABLE III

Influence of capacitance, introduced in L. T. in series with the detector, on the Joshi effect in oxygen.

$pO_2 = 27$ mm (20°). Temperature = 33°. Frequency of A. C. supply = 50 cyc./sec.
 Detector = Vacuo-junction. Source of radiations = Three 200 volt, 200 watt (glass) bulbs, 22 cm. from the ozoniser.

$\frac{C_2 (\mu F)}{V}$		0.	0.00025.	0.0005	0.001.
0.67	i_D	10.77	8.00	7.87	6.93
	i_L	6.26	2.83	4.24	4.24
	Δi	4.52	2.17	3.63	2.69
	% Δi	42	43.4	46.1	38.8
0.93	i_D	12.61	8.25	10.81	11.36
	i_L	8.60	5.39	6.93	7.14
	Δi	4.01	2.84	3.88	4.22
	% Δi	31.8	34.4	35.9	37.2
1.2	i_D	12.13	8.66	10.86	10.95
	i_L	9.00	5.66	7.14	7.49
	Δi	3.13	3.00	3.72	3.47
	% Δi	25.8	34.6	34.3	31.7
1.47	i_D	11.84	8.43	10.44	10.66
	i_L	9.27	5.83	7.42	7.62
	Δi	2.57	2.60	3.02	3.06
	% Δi	21.7	30.8	28.9	28.7
1.67	i_D	11.79	7.87	10.1	10.44
	i_L	10.00	5.92	7.62	7.87
	Δi	1.79	1.95	2.48	2.57
	% Δi	15.2	24.8	24.6	24.6
2.27	i_D	12.46	7.81	9.33	9.59
	i_L	10.77	6.00	7.62	7.87
	Δi	1.69	1.81	1.71	1.72
	% Δi	13.6	23.2	18.3	17.9
2.67	i_D	12.96	7.95	9.59	
	i_L	11.96	6.00	8.06	
	Δi	1.00	1.95	1.53	
	% Δi	7.7	18.4	16	

TABLE IV

Variation with capacitance, introduced in L.T. in parallel to the detector, of the Joshi effect in oxygen.

$pO_2 = 27 \text{ mm. } (20^\circ)$. Temperature $= 32^\circ$. Frequency of A.C. supply $= 50 \text{ cyc./sec.}$ Detector = Vacuo-junction. Source of radiations = Three 200 volt, 200 watt (glass) bulbs, 22 cm. from the ozoniser.

$C_1 \text{ (FP)}$								
V		0	0.0001.	0.00025.	0.0005.	0.001.	0.005.	0.01.
(kV, r.m.s.)								
0.67	i_D	11.53	12.46	12.09	10.15	9.85	9.00	8.60
	i_L	6.03	7.28	7.21	6.08	5.57	5.34	5.1
	Δi	4.9	5.18	4.88	4.07	4.28	3.66	3.5
	$\% \Delta i$	42.5	41.6	40.4	40.1	43.5	40.7	40.7
0.93	i_D	12.04	13.08	12.49	10.61	10.49	9.54	9.33
	i_L	8.43	9.00	8.60	7.69	7.92	6.99	6.75
	Δi	3.01	4.08	3.83	2.95	2.57	2.61	2.58
	$\% \Delta i$	30	31.2	30.7	27.8	27.4	27.4	27.7
1.2	i_D	11.62	12.61	12.28	10.58	10.40	9.33	9.22
	i_L	8.66	9.27	9.00	8.06	7.94	7.31	7.00
	Δi	2.90	3.34	3.28	2.52	2.46	2.12	2.22
	$\% \Delta i$	25.5	26.5	26.7	23.8	23.7	22.7	24.1
1.47	i_D	11.75	12.69	12.21	10.54	10.40	9.43	9.23
	i_L	9.38	9.85	9.61	8.66	8.49	7.84	7.52
	Δi	2.37	2.84	2.57	1.88	1.91	1.59	1.70
	$\% \Delta i$	20.2	22.4	21.0	17.8	18.4	16.9	18.4
1.87	i_D	12.04	13.15	12.53	11.00	10.81	9.8	9.54
	i_L	10.15	10.86	10.63	9.43	9.38	8.60	8.37
	Δi	1.69	2.29	1.90	1.57	1.43	1.2	1.17
	$\% \Delta i$	15.7	17.4	15.2	14.3	13.2	12.3	12.3
2.27	i_D	12.73	13.64	13.23	11.53	11.62	10.63	10.35
	i_L	11.09	11.70	11.45	10.14	10.30	9.54	9.33
	Δi	1.64	1.94	1.78	1.39	1.32	1.09	1.02
	$\% \Delta i$	12.9	14.2	13.5	11.7	11.4	10.3	9.9
2.67	i_D	13.68	14.53	14.25	12.73	12.61	11.84	11.52
	i_L	12.41	13.04	12.76	11.79	11.62	11.00	10.77
	Δi	1.27	1.49	1.49	7.4	0.99	0.84	0.85
	$\% \Delta i$	9.3	10.3	10.5	9.94	7.9	7.1	7.3

TABLE V

The Joshi effect in oxygen with different modes of current detection.

$pO_2 = 27$ mm. (20°). Temperature = 22°–25°. Frequency of A. C. supply = 50 cyc./sec.
Source of radiations = Three 230 volt, 200 watt (glass) bulbs, 22 cm. from the ozoniser.

V (kV, r.m.s.).	Cambridge μ A. Westector rectifier. Vacuo-junction.	Diode 6118 (RCA)		Triode 80 (RCA)		Pentode 6J7 (ROA)	
				Anode bend		Grid leak	
		I.C.	R.C.	I.C.	R.C.	I.C.	R.C.
0.53	i_D	1.41	—	9	—	—	—
	i_L	1.41	—	9	—	—	—
	Δi	—	—	—	—	—	—
	% Δi	—	—	—	—	—	—
0.56	i_D	1.43	—	10	—	—	—
	i_L	1.43	—	12	—	—	—
	Δi	—	—	+2	—	—	—
	% Δi	—	—	+20	—	—	—
0.59	i_D	5.44	8	19	—	—	41
	i_L	5.70	42	21	—	—	83
	Δi	0.74	+39	+2	—	—	+42
	% Δi	17.8	+1300	+10.5	—	—	+102
0.61	i_D	8.57	54	28	40	—	81
	i_L	7.11	83	30	151	—	120
	Δi	1.46	+9	+4	+111	—	+39
	% Δi	17.0	+16.7	+15.3	+278	—	+48.2
0.64	i_D	10.84	84	88	101	—	125
	i_L	8.28	84	39	215	—	141
	Δi	2.56	—	+3	+81	—	+19
	% Δi	23.6	—	+3.3	+50	—	+15.2
0.67	i_D	11.85	128	55	298	—	212
	i_L	8.80	101	51.5	208	—	166
	Δi	2.80	27	3.5	—	—	47
	% Δi	25.2	21.1	6.4	—	—	22.2
0.69	i_D	12.06	140	63	375	—	240
	i_L	9.57	114	59	312	—	181
	Δi	2.49	32	4	63	—	59
	% Δi	20.7	21.9	6.4	16.7	—	24.6
0.72	i_D	12.27	147	71	386	—	262
	i_L	9.82	112	67	292	—	158
	Δi	2.65	35	4	94	—	74
	% Δi	21.6	23.8	5.0	24.4	—	26.2
0.75	i_D	12.45	145	70.5	351	—	270
	i_L	9.67	112	73	272	—	193
	Δi	2.81	33	3.5	79	—	77
	% Δi	22.5	22.8	4.6	22.5	—	28.5
0.77	i_D	12.78	147	81	385	—	280
	i_L	9.97	108	78	284	—	195
	Δi	2.81	39	3	71	—	85
	% Δi	22	26.5	3.7	21.2	—	30.4

(The above observations were made with a comparatively sensitive voltmeter for measuring V.)

TABLE V (contd.)

V (kV, r.m.s.)		Cambridge P.A.	Westector recdifer.	Vacuo-junction.	Diode 6H6 (RCA)		Triode 80 (RCA)				Pentode 6J7 (RCA)	
					I.C.	R.C.	Anode bend		Grid leak		I.C.	R.C.
							I.C.	R.C.	I.C.	R.C.		
0.67	i_D	3	11	4.00	68	55	105	89	179	30	146	48
	i_L	3	11	3.08	50	51.5	82	35	141	27	104	43
	Δi	-	-	0.92	18	3.5	23	4	98	3	42	5
	$\% \Delta i$	-	-	23	28.5	6.1	21.9	10.8	21.2	10.0	28.8	10.4
0.8	i_D	7.5	24	4.9	131	86	147	75		57	168	68
	i_L	0.5	23	3.41	96	63	103	71		56	118	64
	Δi	1.0	1	1.09	38	3	44	4		1	70	4
	$\% \Delta i$	13.3	4.2	22.2	28.3	3.5	29.9	5.3		1.8	37.2	5.9
0.93	i_D	0.5	31	4.95	133	122	112	105	173	81	182	94
	i_L	9.0	33	4.00	99	120	102	103	105	61	118	91
	Δi	0.5	1	0.05	34	2	40	2	8	-	64	3
	$\% \Delta i$	5.3	2.9	19.2	25.0	1.6	29.2	1.9	4.6	-	35.2	3.2
1.07	i_D	12.5	47	5.1	129	158	130	145		90	179	120
	i_L	12.0	46.5	4.47	105	158	98	113		90	120	117
	Δi	0.5	0.5	0.63	24	-	34	2		-	59	3
	$\% \Delta i$	4.0	1.1	12.4	18.6	-	20.2	1.4		-	33	2.5
1.2	i_D	16	60	5.29	127	201.5	129	185	179	110	175	148
	i_L	15.5	60	4.69	107	201.5	101	185	171	110	124	148
	Δi	0.5	-	0.60	2	-	28	-	8	-	61	-
	$\% \Delta i$	3.1	-	11.3	15.7	-	21.7	-	4.5	-	29.3	-
1.33	i_D	19.5	74	5.48	127	251	135	235		125	170	174
	i_L	19.5	74	4.9	111.5	251	108	235		125	124	174
	Δi	-	-	0.58	15.5	-	27	-		-	46	-
	$\% \Delta i$	-	-	10.8	12.2	-	20.0	-		-	27.1	-
1.47	i_D	23.5	86.5	5.75	129		151		183		169	
	i_L	23.5	86.5	5.29	116		126		178		130	
	Δi	-	-	0.46	13		25		5		39	
	$\% \Delta i$	-	-	8	10.1		16.6		2.7		29.1	
1.6	i_D	28.5	102.5	5.98	130		164				175	
	i_L	28.5	102.5	5.57	121		145				140	
	Δi	-	-	0.39	9		19				35	
	$\% \Delta i$	-	-	6.5	6.9		11.6				20.0	

TABLE V (contd.)

V (kV, r.m.s.)		Cambridge μ A.	Westector rectifier.	Vacuo-junction.	Diode 6H6 (RCA)¹		Triode 30 (RCA)		Pentode 6J7 (RCA)			
							Anode bend		Grid leak			
					I.C.	R.C.	I.C.	R.C.	I.C.	R.C.	I.C.	R.C.
1.73	i_D	34	116	6.29	135	183	183			190		
	i_L	34	116	5.92	127	163	178			156		
	Δi	—	—	0.37	8	20	5			34		
	% Δi	—	—	5.9	5.9	10.9	2.7			17.9		
1.87	i_D	40	180	6.68	189	206				200		
	i_L	40	130	6.29	183.5	186				166		
	Δi	—	—	0.34	5.5	20				34		
	% Δi	—	—	5.1	4	9.7				17.0		
2	i_D	46	144	7.00	145	226	185.5			207		
	i_L	46	144	6.71	140	207	181.5			174		
	Δi	—	—	0.29	5	19	4			33		
	% Δi	—	—	4.1	3.4	8.4	2.2			15.9		
2.18	i_D	53	159	7.85	152	249				217		
	i_L	53	159	7.14	148.5	237				189		
	Δi	—	—	0.21	3.5	12				28		
	% Δi	—	—	2.9	2.3	4.8				12.9		
2.27	i_D	60.5	173	7.81	159	274	186			224		
	i_L	60.5	173	7.65	157	259	182			197		
	Δi	—	—	0.16	2	15	4			27		
	% Δi	—	—	2.0	1.3	5.5	2.2			12.3		
2.4	i_D	68	188	8.31	169	300				229		
	i_L	68	189	8.06	167.5	290.5				205.5		
	Δi	—	—	0.25	1.5	9.5				23.5		
	% Δi	—	—	3.0	0.9	3.2				10.3		
2.53	i_D	77.5	198	8.83	181	323	186			235		
	i_L	77.5	198	8.57	180	314	182			212		
	Δi	—	—	0.26	1	9	4			23		
	% Δi	—	—	2.9		2.8	2.2			9.9		
2.67	i_D	86.5	209	9.38	192	348				240		
	i_L	86.5	209	9.14	191	340				218		
	Δi	—	—	0.19	1	8				22		
	% Δi	—	—	2.0		2.3				9.2		
2.8	i_D	94.5	226.5	9.77	203	374	186			244		
	i_L	94.5	226.5	9.7	202	370	184			225		
	Δi	—	—	0.07	1	4	2			19		
	% Δi	—	—	0.7		1.1	1.1			7.9		

(I.C. = Inductive coupling; R.C. = Resistive coupling)

For grid leak detection, a 0.00025 μF capacitance shunted with Dubilier type resistances R_1 was introduced in the grid circuit. The grid was returned to the positive of the two volt filament cell. The negative of the cell (and hence also the filament) was earthed. The plate was given a positive potential of 40 volts. The anode current was determined with the galvanometer G. A series of observations was made with R_1 varied over 1-5 Ma.

(f) *Pentode 6J7 (RCA)*.—The tube was coupled with the L.T., both inductively and resistively. The control grid was given a negative bias of 6 volts. The suppressor and the cathode of the thermionic tube were earthed. The plate was given a positive potential of 220 volts, and the screen of 100 volts. The filament was heated at 280 mA obtained from a battery of 3 storage cells. The current in the plate circuit was observed with the galvanometer G,

D I S C U S S I O N

The Joshi Effect in Different Components of the Discharge Current.—Results in Table I show that similar to the observations of Joshi (*Curr. Sci.*, 1945, 14, 67) in chlorine, both Δi and $\% \Delta i$ in oxygen are greater for the high than for the low frequency components of i . Further, it is seen that whilst Δi for the total unfiltered current is greater than that for H.F., the relative effect $\% \Delta i$ for the latter is sensibly greater than that for the former. Thus e.g., the values for Δi at 1.2 kV for the unfiltered current, the H.F. and the L.F. are respectively 3.56, 3.03 and 0.71; the corresponding values of $\% \Delta i$ are respectively 25.5, 28.6 and 15.5. Increase of the exciting V reduces progressively both Δi and $\% \Delta i$ in all the three cases.

The magnitude of i , both in dark and under irradiation, at a given applied V is in the order: unfiltered $>$ H.F. $>$ L.F. Thus e.g., at the above V, its values in dark are respectively 13.96, 10.58 and 4.58.

The oscillographic studies of Joshi (*ibid.*, 1944, 13, 253; *Nature*, 1944, 154, 147) have revealed that i consists of high frequency i_{HF} , low frequency i_{LF} and the supply frequency component i_s . Thus, added vectorially

$$i = i_{HF} + i_{LF} + i_s.$$

Under irradiation, there occurs an instantaneous and reversible diminution of the amplitudes of especially the high frequency components of i , indicating that the latter constitute the chief seat of the Δi phenomenon. That in oxygen as well the Joshi effect preponderates in the H.F. region of i is evident from the foregoing results.

Influence of Resistive Impedance.—From data in Table II, it is seen that both i_D and i_L , Δi and $\% \Delta i$ are markedly reduced due to a non-inductive resistance R introduced in the L.T. circuit. This inhibition of i , Δi and $\% \Delta i$ due to R is found, in agreement with the observation of Joshi (*Proc. Ind. Acad.*

Sci., 1945, A22, 225) in chlorine, to be more pronounced at small rather than at large values of R . Thus e.g., i_D at 1.2 kV is 13.15 when $R=0 \Omega$; the corresponding values of Δi and $\% \Delta i$ are respectively 3.4 and 25.9. Increase of R to 1 k Ω reduces i_D , Δi and $\% \Delta i$ to 7.75, 1.42 and 18.3 respectively; further increase in R to 10 k Ω , however, decreases i_D , Δi and $\% \Delta i$ only to 5.75, 0.85 and 14.8 respectively.

The Siemens' ozoniser (Joshi, *Curr. Sci.*, 1947, 16, 19) is essentially a compound condenser constituted of three serial capacities: two due to the inner and outer electrode walls and a third associated with the gas in the annular space. Above the 'threshold potential' V_m' , the gas breaks down as a dielectric: the corresponding capacity may therefore be considered as a condenser shunted by an ohmic resistance. From general considerations of a oscillatory discharge of a condenser (such as the ozoniser) in a resistive circuit, Joshi (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1945, A22, 225) showed that R mainly damped the high frequency components of i . This was confirmed by his oscillographic studies of Δi under various R , and the observed reduction in the corresponding aerial current which is predominately H.F. Since the Joshi effect is preferentially incident in the region of high frequencies produced under the discharge (*vide supra*), the observed decrease in Δi and $\% \Delta i$ due to R follows.

It is of interest to note that the voltage across the ozoniser, as measured by a Kelvin-White electrostatic voltmeter, does not vary sensibly due to the introduction of R . This is due to the fact that R , which is of the order of a few thousand ohms, is very small compared with the resistance of the ozoniser itself.

Influence of Capacitative Changes.—In agreement with the general findings of Joshi (*ibid.*, 1945, A22, 225), it is observed (Tables III and IV) that the magnitude of the effect in oxygen is sensibly altered by capacitative changes in the system. The effect of a capacitance is greater when it is added in series than when it is introduced in parallel to the detector.

Whereas Δi without capacitance decreases from 4.52 at 0.67 kV to 1.00 at 2.67 kV, Δi with a serial capacitance C_2 first increases to a maximum at 0.93 kV and then decreases at higher V (Table III). Thus e. g., with $C_2 = 0.0005 \mu\text{F}$, Δi increases from 3.63 at 0.67 kV to a maximum of 3.88 at 0.93 kV, and decreases with further rise in V to 1.53 at 2.67 kV. It is also seen that with $C_2 = 0.00025 \mu\text{F}$, Δi below 1.47 kV is less than that without C_2 ; above 1.47 kV it is the reverse. Thus, values for Δi at 0.93 and 1.87 kV are respectively 4.01 and 1.79 without C_2 and 2.84 and 1.95 with the above capacitance. With higher C_2 , viz., 0.0005 and 0.001 μF , Δi above 0.93 kV is greater than that without C_2 , whereas below 0.93 kV Δi without C_2 is greater. At 0.67 and 1.2 kV, e. g., values for Δi are respectively 4.52 and 3.13 without C_2 , and 3.63 and 3.72 with 0.0005 μF . The Δi - V curves for $C_2 = 0.0005$ and 0.001 μF coincide above 1.2 kV.

The relative effect $\% \Delta i$ is increased markedly due to C_2 (Table III). The effect is most pronounced with the smallest capacitance, viz., 0.00025 μF and at higher V. With higher C_2 , viz., 0.0005 and 0.001 μF , $\% \Delta i$ is smaller than that with 0.00025 μF . Thus, with $C_2 = 0, 0.00025, 0.0005$ and $0.001 \mu\text{F}$, values for $\% \Delta i$ at 2.27 kV are respectively 13.6, 23.2, 18.3 and 17.9, and at 1.2 kV, 25.8, 34.6, 34.3 and 31.7. The increase in $\% \Delta i$ on the introduction of a serial capacitance in the L.T. circuit, provides another proof for the observation that in oxygen, as in chlorine, the Joshi effect preponderates in the high frequency region of i .

The net effect Δi increases as a result of introduction of a parallel capacitance $C_1 = 0.0001 \mu\text{F}$ (Table IV). At 1.2 kV, e.g., Δi with and without the above capacitance is respectively 3.34 and 2.95. With increase of C_1 , Δi decreases. It is, at the above V, 3.28 for 0.00025 μF and 2.22 for 0.01 μF .

Since i_{HF} , which represents the main seat of the phenomenon, is by-passed by C_1 , a reduction in $\% \Delta i$ is to be anticipated. This is actually observed (Table IV) For instance, values for $\% \Delta i$ at 1.47 kV with and without $C_1 = 0.0005 \mu\text{F}$ are respectively 20.2 and 17.8. As has been already pointed out, the effect of C_1 added in parallel to the vacuo-junction is small in comparison with that of C_2 introduced in series with the detector.

The Joshi Effect with Different Modes of Current Detection.—That V_m , at which i increases rapidly with the applied V, is a fundamental quantity is brought out by the results of these investigations. Despite widely varying methods of current detection, this potential for the ozoniser containing oxygen at a pressure of 27 mm. (20°) is a constant quantity of 0.6 kV, the other factors, viz., the frequency of the A.C. supply and the temperature, being (sensibly) constant.

From Table V, it is evident that in agreement with the results of earlier work in chlorine (Joshi, *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1943, Part II, pp. 70-75; *Curr. Sci.*, 1945, 14, 67; Prasad, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1946, 20, 187) and bromine (Tewari, *ibid.*, 1948, 22, 553) in these laboratories, the magnitude of the Joshi effect in oxygen varies apparently with the mode of current detection. Thus e.g., at 0.93 kV, $\% \Delta i$ is 19.2 with a vacuo-junction. With the two crystal detectors, viz., the Cambridge A.C. micro-ammeter and the Westector rectifier, values for $\% \Delta i$ at the above V are comparatively low, being 5.3 and 2.9 respectively. This is also the case with a diode 6H6 (1.6), a triode 30 (anode bend 1.9; grid leak 0.0) and a pentode 6J7 (3.2) coupled resistively, and the triode, fed inductively but used as a grid leak detector (4.6). On the other hand, $\% \Delta i$ is comparatively high, viz., 35.2, 28.2, and 25.6 when i is detected respectively with the pentode, the triode used as anode bend detector and the diode, all the thermionic tubes being fed inductively. The apparent variability of the magnitude of the effect with the mode of current detection arises from the selectivity in response of the various detectors to different frequencies in the spectrum of the discharge current.

As has already been pointed out, the magnitude of the Joshi effect, determined with the crystal detectors, is very small. Thus e.g., the maximum observed with the Cambridge A.C. micro-ammeter is 13.3%, and with the Westinghouse instrument, 4.2%, both at 0.8 kV. With increasing V, the effect decreases and finally disappears, at 1.33 kV in the case of the former and at 1.2 kV with the latter. A crystal detector consists of a crystal in contact with a metal. The boundary between the crystal and the metal possesses a very high resistance, the value of which varies markedly with the direction of the impressed e.m.f., thus leading to rectification (Grondahl, *Rev. Mod. Phys.*, 1933, 5, 141; Wilson, "Semiconductors and Metals", Camb. Univ. Press, 1939). That the magnitude of Δi obtained with crystal detectors is small might, in part, be due to the appreciable resistance of the rectifier in the low-resistance direction, especially at small voltages applied across the instrument.

As compared with the crystal detectors, the magnitude of Δi observed with the vacuo-junction is considerable, the maximum being 23% at 0.67 kV. With increase in V, $\% \Delta i$ decreases and falls below 1.0 near about 2.8 kV. The net effect Δi is maximum at 0.8 kV, after which it decreases with V. According to Joshi (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1945, A 22, 225), the vacuo-junctions have a stable characteristic over a wide range of applied V and frequency of the A.C. supply. For large currents or high frequencies, however, errors due to the 'skin effect' creep in. Further, since in this mode of current detection an appreciable resistance is introduced, a reduction of the H.F. oscillations occurs prior to irradiation. This would reduce Δi . In a thermal device like the vacuo-junction, reduction in Δi due to resistive damping of i_{HF} is, however, not appreciable, since the corresponding loss is represented by conversion into heat. Due to the stray capacity between the heater wire and the thermocouple, on the other hand, high frequencies may find their way into the thermocouple circuit and may consequently be lost.

The maximum Δi (28.3% at 0.8 kV) obtained with the inductively fed diode is higher than that obtained with the vacuo-junction. This is to be anticipated in view of the low ohmic resistance in the oscillatory circuit. The net effect Δi is also maximum at 0.8 kV. With increase in V beyond 0.8 kV, both Δi and $\% \Delta i$ decrease; their magnitudes become negligibly small near about 2.4 kV. The effect obtained with the diode, resistively coupled with the L. T. of the ozoniser, is small. The maximum photo-suppression observed is 6.4% at 0.67 kV; at potentials higher than 0.93 kV, there is no photo-effect. That the magnitude of Δi is small is due to the fact that in this mode of current detection a high resistance is introduced in the oscillatory circuit; this increases the damping constant and also the 'skin effect', leading to a reduction of the H.F. oscillations prior to irradiation.

The triode used as an anode bend detector and coupled inductively with L. T. shows a Δi which is larger than that obtained with a diode coupled similarly; the maximum is 29.9% at 0.8 kV (Table V). On the other hand,

$\% \Delta i$ observed with the triode used as a grid leak detector is small. Thus, with a leak resistance of 5 M Ω , $\% \Delta i$ is maximum (21.2) at 0.67 kV, and decreases abruptly to 4.6 at 0.93 kV; with further rise in V, it decreases but slowly (Table V). Decreasing the leak resistance, whilst maintaining the capacitance constant, reduces the value of maximum Δi . Thus, with leaks of 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1 M Ω , the maximum values of $\% \Delta i$ observed are respectively 21.2, 18.2, 10.3, 13.7 and 10.7, all at 0.67 kV. The magnitude of Δi observed with the triode fed resistively is small.

The inductively fed pentode shows largest Δi , the maximum observed being 37.2% at 0.8 kV. At higher V, both Δi and $\% \Delta i$ decrease, but $\% \Delta i$ in this case is appreciable even at 2.8 kV; at this potential other detectors show nil or negligible photo-suppression.

In the preliminary work on this effect in oxygen in these laboratories Cheriau (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1942, Part III, *Chem. Sec.*, Abst. No. 56) who used a crystal detector observed a positive effect $+\Delta i$ at low V. A like phenomenon has been observed by the present author with thermionic tube detectors. Under identical conditions of excitation, the vacuo-junction, however, shows nil or the negative effect. When produced, the positive effect is large below V_m , at the point at which the current just begins to grow, decreases rapidly with V, and changes sign at potentials above V_m , after passing in many cases through a nul-point. Thus e.g., with the diode coupled inductively, a current gain of 1300% is observed at 0.59 kV. Increase of V to 0.61 kV reduces $+\Delta i$ to 16.7%. At 0.64 kV, no change is observed in i under irradiation. With further increase in V, there occurs the negative effect, the magnitude of which increases to a maximum and then decreases. With the diode fed resistively, $+\Delta i$ is small, but decreases gradually with V; further, it is distributed over a comparatively wide range of V. The observations with triode and pentode are generally similar to those with the diode coupled inductively.

The nature of potential variation of Δi and $\% \Delta i$ is not, as is evident from the above, altered by a mere change in the mode of current detection. Thus, both Δi and $\% \Delta i$ are maximum near 0.8 kV, after which they decrease with the applied V. This observation is in agreement with the general findings of Joshi (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1945, A22, 389) that $\% \Delta i$ is a maximum near V_m , and decreases thereafter with the applied V.

Grateful thanks of the author are due to Professor S. S. Joshi for having suggested the problem and for his keen interest in the work, and to Mr. G. S. Kamath, M. Sc., for his kind help in a part of the work.